

Anomalous Kinetic Behaviour of Methyl and Methoxy Derivatives on the Oxidation of Phenacyl Bromides by Cerium(IV) in Sulphuric Acid Medium

B. HARI KISHAN and E. V. SUNDARAM

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 23 May 1985, accepted 11 September 1985

The kinetics of cerium(IV) oxidation of *p*-methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides have been investigated in 40-70% (v/v) acetic acid containing varying concentrations of sulphuric acid. The reactions are first order with respect to [oxidant] as well as [substrate]. The reactions are acid-catalysed and the absence of water molecule participation is indicated and discussed through Hammett's acidity and Bunnett's plots. The kinetic behaviour of these derivatives differ from the phenacyl bromide and its electron withdrawing substituents, like *p*-Br, *m*-Br, *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂, mainly in the acid dependent paths and in thermodynamic parameters. Hence, a different probable mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of *p*-methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides.

THE cerium(IV) oxidation of phenacyl bromide and its electron withdrawing substituents, like *p*-Br, *m*-Br, *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂, in sulphuric acid medium was previously found¹ to occur through free radical mechanism, where the slow step of the mechanism involves the attack of cerium(IV) monomer Ce(SO₄)²⁺ on keto form of the phenacyl bromide and the attack of a water molecule as a nucleophile on carbonyl carbon. The rate of the reaction is accelerated by the electron withdrawing substituents. In order to ascertain, and to obtain more information on the substituent effects, similar studies are extended using electron donating substituents, such as *p*-methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides under similar conditions.

Experimental

p-Methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides were prepared by usual methods, such as the bromination of the corresponding acetophenones in ice-cold condition and recrystallised from alcohol before use. The acetic acid used was AnalaR, twice refluxed and distilled with chromium trioxide. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions of *p*-methyl- or *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides were prepared by dissolving the required amount in 100% acetic acid and the stock solutions of cerium(IV) sulphate were freshly prepared in 5 *M* sulphuric acid and standardised¹ by Fe^{II} solution. The method employed to follow the reaction is the same as described earlier^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometric studies reveal that three moles of cerium(IV) were reduced per mole of *p*-methyl- or *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromide. The products

obtained are corresponding benzoic acids and formaldehydes. The identification of products has been done by usual methods^{1,2}.

The oxidation reaction for *p*-methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides in sulphuric acid containing 60% (v/v) of acetic acid showed first order dependence on [substrate] as well as [cerium(IV)] (Table 1). The plot of k_1 against [substrate] is linear passing through origin, indicating the order with respect to substrate is one. Although the first order plots are linear for all the concentrations of cerium(IV), the rate constant k_1 is not independent of initial [cerium(IV)]. The rate constant k_1 decreases with the increase of [cerium(IV)] (Table 1). This may be due to the principal equilibrium between monomeric and unreactive trimeric cerium(IV) in aqueous acetic and sulphuric acid media¹.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH¹ [SUBSTRATE] AND [OXIDANT]

[H₂SO₄]=3.0 *M*, CH₃COOH=60% (v/v), Temp.=318 K

[sub] × 10 ³ <i>M</i>	[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ³ <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
		A	B
0.8	4.0	3.60	1.70
1.0	4.0	4.61	2.00
1.5	4.0	6.42	3.08
2.0	4.0	8.27	4.22
3.0	4.0	12.60	6.40
2.0	2.0	11.12	6.32
2.0	3.0	9.64	5.14
2.0	6.0	6.00	3.00
2.0	8.0	4.65	2.15

A = *p*-Methylphenacyl bromide, B = *p*-methoxyphenacyl bromide.

The effect of solvent acetic acid on rate was studied from 40 to 70% (v/v) (Table 2). It is

observed that the rate increases with the increase in percentage of acetic acid. Plot of $\log k_1$ against $1/D$ is fairly linear with a positive slope indicating that the process is of cation-dipole type⁸.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACETIC ACID ON RATE CONSTANT, k_1

$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]=0.004 \text{ M}$, $[\text{sub.}]=0.01 \text{ M}$, Temp. = 318 K

Substrate	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at acetic acid % (v/v)*			
	40 (45.73)	50 (39.17)	60 (32.60)	70 (26.04)
<i>p</i> -Methylphenacyl bromide	2.60	2.86	4.61	9.26
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenacyl bromide	1.00	1.05	2.00	6.44

* Values in parentheses are dielectric constant.

Table 3 shows the increase of pseudo-first order rate constants with the increase of concentration of sulphuric acid. The plots of $\log k_1$ against $\log [\text{H}^+]$ were linear with slope values about four which do not indicate any meaning. The Hammett's plots of $\log k_1$ against $-\text{H}_0$ were linear for *p*-methyl and *p*-methoxy derivatives with slopes 1.05 and 1.20, respectively. These unit slopes indicate that most probably no water molecule is participating in the rate controlling step. The Bunnett's plots $\log(k_1 + \text{H}_0)$ against $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ are also linear with negative slopes, confirming this fact. The values of $-\text{H}_0$ and $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ at various acidity, were taken from Paul and Long⁴ and Bunnett⁵, assuming that the values do not change much up to 50% acetic acid medium^{6,7}.

The present and previous¹ kinetic data show that *p*-CH₃- and *p*-OCH₃-phenacyl bromides differ from phenacyl bromide and its electron withdrawing substituents, like *p*-Br, *m*-Br, *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂. It is apparent that both the electron withdrawing and

electron donating groups enhance the rate of oxidation (Table 4). This type of anomalous behaviour is not uncommon in the literature of cerium(IV) oxidations. In the oxidation of acetophenones¹⁰ and benzaldehydes¹¹ by cerium(IV), both the electron donating and electron withdrawing substituents enhance the rate of oxidation, whereas in the oxidation of mandalic acids¹² by cerium(IV), the *p*-methoxy derivative shows higher rate with respect to other derivatives. In all the above cases different mechanisms were proposed.

In the present case the oxidation rates of these *p*-CH₃- and *p*-OCH₃-phenacyl bromides appear to be more sensitive towards changes in acid concentration and temperature. In acid effect the Hammett's⁸ plots for phenacyl bromide and its electron withdrawing substituents, gave straight lines but the slope values were much less than unity (0.45 to 0.56), which indicate that with these substrates the slow step of the mechanism involves water molecule participation. This is also confirmed by Bunnett's slopes⁹, which gave curves with positive slopes (from 0 to 2.6). Thus, these observation clearly indicate that a different mechanism is to be proposed for *p*-CH₃ and *p*-OCH₃ derivatives.

Activation parameters, like ΔE^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for the reactions in 3 *M* sulphuric acid for all the phenacyl bromides were determined by measuring the rate constants at five different temperatures (Table 4). It can be seen from Table 4 that the overall activation parameters for phenacyl bromide and its *p*-Br, *m*-Br, *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂ derivatives are very close to each other. Markedly negative ΔS^\ddagger and higher ΔE^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger on the contrary, are found in case of *p*-methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [SULPHURIC ACID] ON RATE CONSTANT, k_1

$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]=0.004 \text{ M}$, $[\text{sub.}]=0.015 \text{ M}$, $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}=(\text{v/v})$, Temp. = 318 K

Phenacyl bromide	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] \text{ M}$						X*	Y*
	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0		
<i>p</i> -Methyl	1.41	3.00	5.24	7.00	13.62	20.00	1.05	-0.3
<i>p</i> -Methoxy	0.64	1.34	2.99	4.69	9.33	17.27	1.20	-2.3

* X = Slope of the Hammett's plot $\log k_1$ vs $-\text{H}_0$, Y = slope of the Bunnett's plot $(\log k_1 + \text{H}_0)$ vs $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN CERIUM(IV)-PHENACYL BROMIDE REACTIONS IN SULPHURIC ACID MEDIUM

$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]=0.004 \text{ M}$, $[\text{sub.}]=0.02 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=3.0 \text{ M}$, $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}=60\% (\text{v/v})$, Temp. = 318 K

Phenacyl bromide	$k_1 \times 10^3$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}
H	1.25	79.83	77.15	31	87.03
<i>p</i> -Br	1.71	82.38	79.70	20	86.19
<i>m</i> -Br	2.02	83.05	80.37	17	85.77
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	3.75	89.42	86.74	8	84.10
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	2.36	86.19	82.51	5	85.35
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	4.21	111.72	109.09	79	83.81
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	2.11	124.50	121.86	114	85.61

Keeping the above observations in view, a different mechanism for oxidation of the *p*-methyl- and *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromides which do not involve water molecule participation in the slow step, is proposed (Scheme 1). Since the reaction follows Hammett's H_0 relation, the mechanistic

Scheme 1

diagnosis of Waters and Littler suggests the formation of a cyclic five-membered transition state involving oxidant and substrate. Scheme 1 shows, the attack of cerium(IV) on *p*-methyl- or *p*-methoxy-phenacyl bromide gives a five-membered ring structure, which disproportionates through C-C bond fission homolytically and forms a resonance stabilised oxonium ion $\text{Y-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}\equiv\text{O}^+$ (where Y is an electron releasing group) and a free radical $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{Br}$. This species is further oxidised by another cerium(IV) ultimately forming formaldehyde. The oxonium ion gives the corresponding benzoic acid. The transition state is supposed to be resonance stabilised because of the electron releasing group Y. If Y is an electron withdrawing group the same can not be expected.

The rate of oxidation is first order with respect to the substrate as well as to cerium(IV) monomer

and has first order dependence on h_0 , and hence, the rate law can be represented as

$$\text{Rate} = k_2[\text{substrate}][\text{Ce(IV)}]_m h_0 \quad (1)$$

where, Ce(IV)_m is cerium monomer. The cerium(IV) monomers, in sulphuric acid medium exists in various forms^{1,2} of sulphate complexes, namely $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2-}$, $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})\text{SO}_4^+$, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}$, $\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{OH})(\text{SO}_4)_2$, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^{2-}$, $\text{H}\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^-$, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^{4-}$, $\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4$, $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$, $\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_5^{2-}$ and $\text{H}\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_5^-$ depending on the concentrations of cerium(IV) and sulphuric acid. The involvement of cerium(IV) cationic species is confirmed through the solvent effect studies. By considering the available data on equilibrium constants^{1,4} for various forms of species and transport numbers and spectrophotometric^{1,5} measurements of cerium(IV) complexes, it can be concluded that most probably the $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}$ is the reactive species, in the present reaction conditions.

In the mechanism proposed earlier¹ for electron withdrawing substituents the slow step involves a water molecule participation through a non-cyclic transition state.

References

1. B. H. KISHAN and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1079.
2. B. H. KISHAN and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 322.
3. S. GLASSSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "Theory of Rate Process", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941, p. 439.
4. F. A. LONG and M. A. PAUL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1957, **57**, 1.
5. J. F. BUNNETT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4956.
6. D. S. NOYCE and P. CASTELFRANCO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **73**, 4483.
7. K. B. WIBERG and J. R. EVANS, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1970, p. 150.
8. L. P. HAMMETT, "Physical Organic Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1940, Ch. IX.
9. H. S. ROCHESTER, "Acidity Functions", Academic Press, New York, 1970, p. 110.
10. G. P. PANIGRAHI and P. K. MISRO, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1976, **83**, 211.
11. K. B. WIBERG and P. C. FORD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 124.
12. F. G. CALVARUSA, P. CAVASINO and G. SBRIZIDO, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1981, **13**, 1029.
13. B. H. KISHAN, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, 1984, p. 115.
14. T. J. HARDWICK and E. ROBERTSON, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 818, 828.
15. T. N. BONDAVEVA, V. F. BARKOVSKI and T. V. VRLIKANOVA, *Z. Neorg. Khim.*, 1965, **10**, 127.